

IPBES invasive alien species assessment, data management report for Figure SPM.5 and Chapter 3.

Figure 3.34 Assessment of the relative importance of indirect and direct drivers in facilitating biological invasions across stages of the invasion process

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Project leader and contributors:

- Philip Hulme (Philip.Hulme@lincoln.ac.nz) and Vigdis Vandvik (Vigdis.Vandvik@uib.no)
- Asuka Koyama
- Anthony Ricciardi
- Ryan Blanchard
- Rafael Xavier
- Esra Per
- Tohru Ikeda
- Carolina Morales
- Morelia Camacho-Cervantes
- Nirmalie Pallewatta
- Linus Munishi
- Jan Pergl
- Ileana Herrera

Data curator:

- Tanara Renard Truong

Description

This figure shows the relative importance of the 12 drivers of biodiversity change for each invasion stage (introduction, transport, establishment and spread) across and within realms (terrestrial, freshwater, marine) and broad taxonomic units (microbes, plants, invertebrates, vertebrates)

Process overview

A. Expert-based assessment

The relative importance of the 12 drivers of biodiversity change for each invasion stage across and within realms (terrestrial, freshwater, marine) and broad taxonomic units (microbes, plants, invertebrates, vertebrates) was quantified through an expert-based assessment, carried out in two rounds, following the delphi method.

B. Consolidation of results – comparison with the analysis of the literature reviewed for each section

The literature reviewed for this chapter (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5529310>) was analyzed to show the number of papers reviewed for each driver at each stage. This result was then compared with the expert-based assessment scores.

Protocol**A. Expert-based assessment**

The relative importance of the 12 drivers of biodiversity change for each invasion stage across and within realms (terrestrial, freshwater, marine) and broad taxonomic units (microbes, plants, invertebrates, vertebrates) was quantified through an expert-based assessment, carried out in two rounds, following the delphi method.

1. First Round – October 2021 (FILE A)

Each member of the chapter 3 author team (coordinating lead, lead, fellows) individually scored the relative importance of each driver as a percentage (i.e., distributing 100 importance points across drivers) for each of the four stages of the invasion process. The exercise was done separately for each realm and taxonomic unit, and the authors based their judgement on the evidence gathered in the chapter. The scores of all panel members were then averaged to produce an overall consensus assessment.

2. Second Round – August 2022 (FILE B)

In the second round, authors were allowed to adjust their individual scores based on the consensus scores and the content of updated chapter draft, and the final consensus agreement was then produced as the averages of these adjusted scores.

B. Consolidation of results – comparison with the analysis of the literature reviewed for each section (FILE C)

The literature reviewed for this chapter (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5529310>) was analyzed to show the number of papers reviewed for each driver at each stage. This analysis was then compared with the expert-based assessment scores. Results show that both the analysis and the expert-based assessment reach the same conclusions